

Career Readiness of the Pre-Service Teachers of San Isidro College

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the career readiness of the Pre-Service Teachers (PSTs) of San Isidro College. The study used the descriptive method to describe the general findings of the study in the form of a questionnaire with a 4-point scale to collect the information from the Pre-Service Teachers of the School of Education. This study used purposive sampling with the 52 Pre-Service Teachers. The result implies that in terms of career readiness of the Pre-Service Teachers in the aspect of competencies, they excel in terms of collaboration/teamwork, while in their critical thinking and oral/written communication, they got the lowest among the parameters. The result of the study would be a great help to the School of Education in designing or creating a program to strengthen the competence that is already stable or at its highest level and to improve/enhance those that need improvement to achieve the balance of the competences needed of the Pre-Service Teachers to be effective and efficient in their teaching in time.

Subject Area

Career Readiness

Keywords: *Career Readiness; Critical Thinking; Oral/Written Communication; Team work; Collaboration; Digital Technology; Leadership, Professionalism; Career Management; Global/Intercultural Fluency*

INTRODUCTION

Following the findings of Doe, R. (2015), the primary objective of delivering high-quality education in higher education institutions is to refine the skills of students, instill in them a passion for seeking new knowledge, and ultimately prepare them for gainful employment or the application of these skills to address real-world challenges. The foundational role of human resources in driving a nation's economy is widely acknowledged. However, there is a distinct emphasis on cultivating a skilled and educated workforce capable of addressing future complexities. Despite

the multifaceted nature of education, it serves as a preparatory ground for nurturing responsible citizenship, fostering skilled labor, promoting cultural literacy, nurturing critical thinking abilities, and ensuring global competitiveness, as Jones (2012) highlighted. The contemporary landscape of the 21st-century workforce has undergone substantial transformations in terms of the evolving concept of careers and organizational strategies. Organizations are not solely engaged in competitive downsizing or outsourcing practices; they are strategically focusing on optimizing their human capital to meet the demands of a dynamically changing environment.

Organizations make their selection and hiring decisions based on the credentials and competencies that indicate a potential employee's likelihood of success in the job. These shifts in hiring practices underscore the importance for universities to produce high-caliber, job-ready graduates whose skills extend beyond theoretical classroom knowledge, as highlighted by Freudenberg et al. (2008). Although the transition from secondary to postsecondary education is relatively seamless in terms of skill development and standards, there is a need for a clearly defined, measurable, and evaluative pathway from college or graduate school to successful job performance, as emphasized by Wendler et al. (2012). Graduates today encounter a multitude of credentials, tests, certifications, and networking requirements as they navigate the landscape to secure well-paying jobs within their chosen fields. To address these challenges, universities and colleges provide diverse courses, programs, and promising job opportunities for students upon graduation.

The imperative of being prepared for a career is underscored by the intense global competition among organizations, necessitating the recruitment of well-aligned and well-prepared employees to achieve organizational objectives. A significant shift has occurred from the traditional model, where organizations played a central role in shaping and managing individuals' careers, to a contemporary scenario where individuals actively construct their career paths. Despite this transformation, more research is needed on this evolving dynamic. While organizations are progressively relinquishing control over individuals' career management, the interests and skills of individuals remain crucial elements of organizations' social capital. Neglecting or paying superficial attention to career development can adversely affect an organization's long-term turnover rates and overall performance. Understanding the motivations driving employees to pursue graduate-level degrees and their perceptions of readiness for current or future roles is essential for organizations to derive maximum benefit from their workforce.

This research tried to find out the answer to the following questions on the dominant competencies of the Pre-Service Teachers for career readiness and the least competencies of Pre-Service Teachers to design or create an intervention to enhance the least competence/s that were identified.

The purpose of this research was to find out the career readiness of the Pre- Service Teachers in terms of the eight competencies, namely, critical thinking/problem solving, oral/written, teamwork/collaboration, digital technology, leadership, professionalism/work ethic, career management, and cultural/intercultural fluency. By identifying the dominant and weak competence/competencies, the School of Education can design or create a program that will strengthen/develop the competence/s that they have already demonstrated and make an intervention for their least acquired to equip them for their teaching practice fully.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted at San Isidro College, particularly the School of Education. This institution was founded in July 1949 by Fr. Joseph Reith, SJ. It has existed for almost 75 years, and it offers varied programs. The programs offered are the Bachelor of Secondary Education and Bachelor of Elementary Education. A descriptive research design was used in the study; fifty-two (52) Pre-Service Teachers graduates during the Academic Year 2022-2023 are the study's respondents. Total population sampling is a type of purposive sampling technique that involves examining the entire population; since the number of Pre-Service Teachers was only 52, the researchers took all the PSTs as the study participants. The main variables of the study are the competencies for career readiness, and a four-point scale with indicators enumerated in every competence was used as a data collection instrument. Frequency, percentage, and ANOVA will be used in treating the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 presents the career readiness competence of the pre-service teacher.

Table 1.
Competences for Career Readiness

Parameter	Mean	Std. Dev.	Qual. Desc.
Team Work/Collaboration	3.80	0.068	Very high
Global/Intercultural Fluency	3.69	0.107	Very high
Professionalism	3.68	0.320	Very high
Digital Technology	3.66	0.330	Very high
Career Management	3.63	0.124	Very high
Leadership	3.50	0.285	Very high
Oral/Written Communication	3.40	0.560	Very high
Critical Thinking	3.40	0.256	Very high

The result shows that all the competencies for career readiness are very high in terms of their qualitative description, but when it comes to mean results, they vary from one competence to another. This means that critical thinking and oral/written communication parameters were considered the least among the eight competencies for career readiness. On the other hand, according to Fikriyati et al. (2022), critical thinking has become essential in facing the challenges of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 era. Industrial Revolution 4.0 has both contributions and huge effects on society.

Therefore, the education field must prepare competent Pre-Service Teachers who can compete globally during the Industrial Revolution era. The rapid growth of technology, information, and communication in this era makes our lives easier. It brings a new challenge to the education field, especially for those who will soon be teachers. As a result, the challenge to the academe that offers programs like Bachelor of Elementary Education and Bachelor of Secondary Education is to prepare the Pre-Service Teachers to develop the competencies needed when they are exposed to the field of teaching, and one of these competencies is critical thinking and oral/written communication competencies.

Teamwork/collaboration and global/intercultural fluency garnered the highest mean, implying that for a pre-service teacher, it is important that teamwork/collaboration be given weight because it will help the pre-service teachers grow in their chosen careers. It will also enhance their capacity in terms of teaching strategies, which the co-pre-service Teachers can also share; in this scenario, the opportunity to experience development on areas of the competencies that need further attention will be taken care of.

As cited by Gentry (2012), it says that effective collaboration comes with effort. It is a framework whereby two or more individuals work together as equal partners to make decisions that will lead to positive changes. In an educational setting, collaboration aims to improve student services through the efforts of families and schools working together as equal partners who share resources, decisions, and responsibilities. Collaboration skills are essential for all teachers/Pre-Service Teachers. Through collaboration, families and professionals can combine their strengths and wisdom to make education appropriate for the student. Capitalizing on each other's knowledge and expertise helps the student and makes for stronger families and more competent professionals.

Table 2 presents the comparison of competences for career readiness of the Pre-Service Teachers.

Table 2.
Comparison of Competences for Career Readiness

Parameter	Mean	<i>f</i>	<i>p</i>
Team Work/ Collaboration	3.80		
Global/Intercultural Fluency	3.69		
Professionalism	3.68		
Digital Technology	3.66	23.548	0.029*
Career Management	3.63		
Leadership	3.51		
Critical Thinking	3.40		
Oral/Written Communication	3.40		

* $p < 0.05$

The result shows that the p-value result of the competencies when compared among the Pre-Service Teachers of the Bachelor of Elementary Education and Bachelor of Secondary Education has a significant difference, which means that all the competencies have to be developed or strengthened equally because these are all needed in the growth of the Pre-Service Teachers, especially when they will be out in the field to teach.

Evidence shows that prevention and intervention programs are more successful when teachers work together in teams when it comes to early school leaving. Teachers' teamwork means establishing professional communities of teachers, specialized or interdisciplinary, within one institution or cross-institutional, to work together towards the same positive aim. Teachers' teamwork is an effective strategy to overcome complex pedagogical challenges, such as early school leaving. If they have effective teamwork, teachers have a chance to connect too, to share ideas, insights, encouragement, and mutual support, which is proven to be more effective than working in isolation from one another, and this has always been a prerequisite to establishing an

influential school community. Teamwork is a learning opportunity and creates a place for peer support and resource sharing. Working as a cohesive team has been proven to affect student success positively.

As articulated in the study by Barnett et al. (2020), educators grapple with the challenge of reaching an increasingly diverse student population in a world described as flat (Darling-Hammond, 2015), shrinking (Carreira & Kagan, 2018), interconnected (Kahn & Agnew, 2017), and globalized (Hansen, 2017). The dynamics of the modern classroom are further complicated by the global surge in nativism juxtaposed with widespread intercultural mobility, communication advancements, and evolving technology (Kohli et al., 2017). This juxtaposition highlights intricate tensions in an educational context becoming more interconnected globally.

Effectively addressing this complexity requires educators to possess intercultural competence, especially with students who bring diverse life experiences related to language, culture, race, ethnicity, religion, and socio-economic strata (Scanlan & López, 2014). While there is a consensus that teacher preparation should prioritize intercultural competence, uncertainties persist regarding the specific components of such competence and the most effective approaches for integrating it into teacher preparation programs. This gap underscores the need for further research and exploration in this area.

Ariff et al. (2017) mentioned in their study that professional and professionalism is a key to quality improvement for teachers in the new millennium era. Quality refers to the quality of the process, and the more important is the quality of the product. With this, human resources should be integrated through training, courses, seminars, or programs to ensure that every individual, especially pre-service teachers, can develop their potential optimally (Wardah & Pendililang, 2014). Training, courses, seminars, or programs are steps that institutions must supply to improve the quality of education in the future. The Education system has good earnings and quality human capital as envisioned by the state. The government made various efforts and measures to ensure the quality of the education system improved from time to time. Among the efforts is to enhance the teaching profession (Tajul, 2002).

Teachers' professional practice is a preparation step that pre-service teachers should form. Therefore, teacher preparation institutions need to produce human resources and pre-service teachers who are not only knowledgeable, competent, and even professional at their best. Professionalism is a crucial element in pre-service teacher education. To become a professional educator, one must accept the concept of professionalism.

Gonzales et al. (2021) highlighted in their research that the evolving societal and economic landscape of the 21st century demands new skills and competencies from its citizens. This necessity arises from the need for practical capabilities to actively contribute to economic growth, considering knowledge as the primary asset in the contemporary system. The significance of information and communication technologies (ICT) is a notable aspect of the current societal structure. ICT has assumed a crucial role in education, playing a pivotal part in teaching and learning due to various social, cultural, and health factors on a global scale.

Consequently, educational policies have embraced technology inside and outside the classroom as a fundamental support for training. As a result, students in the 21st century require competencies that empower them to navigate the evolving dynamics of individual information and

knowledge relationships. The education system must adapt to accommodate novel approaches for learners to thrive in this information and knowledge-centric society. Globally, educational policies have prioritized the cultivation of competencies related to ICT use, aligning with the European Union's recognition of digital competence as one of the eight critical skills essential for lifelong learning—a skill now ingrained as a cross-disciplinary competency in all Spanish universities.

Considering these social and educational premises, in university studies of education, it is prioritized to train professionals to be prepared for the pedagogical integration of ICT in teaching and learning.

As referenced by Celk, B. (2017), the investigation conducted by Bruinsma and Jansen (2010) delves into the factors influencing prospective teachers' decisions to pursue a career in teaching and the subsequent impact on their career development. The study revealed that teacher candidates driven by internal factors such as a genuine commitment to the teaching profession, as well as those influenced by external factors like a stable job environment, demonstrated a higher desire for career development compared to candidates influenced by conflicting external factors (e.g., teaching as a fallback profession).

Crucial determinants of the teaching profession's status include the socio-economic background of teachers, their gender, the qualifications of their educational institutions, specialized fields of study, school types (public or private), the geographical location of schools (urban or rural), and the remuneration they receive, as emphasized by Tezcan (1991). This underscores the complexity of evaluating teachers solely as knowledge conveyors; instead, they should be perceived as multifaceted professionals encompassing roles as philosophers, sociologists, pedagogues, psychologists, and adept technocrats.

The significance of teachers' roles is heightened by the expectations placed upon them, underscoring the importance of thoughtful selection, practical training, continuous professional development, and accurate job placement. To meet the demands of evolving educational programs and ensure their flexible implementation, teachers must be well-versed in the fundamentals of program development, as highlighted by Saçlı (1996). Access to diverse educational tools, staying abreast of daily innovations, and effectively utilizing these tools are imperative for educators.

An idealistic teacher's primary responsibility lies in facilitating the intellectual growth of young minds. Achieving this goal involves applying educational theories derived from continuous research efforts, positioning teachers as pivotal in implementing education policies, and developing theories grounded in practical outcomes (Özkan, 2005). In the current era marked by profound and unprecedented societal changes, teachers play a crucial role in comprehending and conveying the significance of these transformations to students.

A comprehensive academic and professional foundation for teachers becomes essential to meet these demands. Academic preparation should encompass a broad understanding of various scientific disciplines, complemented by professional training that delves into various sub-disciplines of pedagogy for a specified duration, as emphasized by Hesapçioğlu (1992). This dual emphasis on academic and professional aspects is vital for effective teacher education.

Xu and Patmor (2012) highlighted the empowering impact of teacher leadership on school improvement. While existing approaches to teacher leadership, such as the Teacher Leader Master

(TLM) degree program and teacher-led professional development, primarily focus on in-service teachers, a noticeable gap exists in addressing teacher leadership training within current teacher preparation curricula. This research article explores three instructional strategies designed to cultivate leadership skills in pre-service teachers within a teacher preparation program. The three strategies are:

1. To encourage cross-domain and multiple perspective-taking among pre-service teachers,
2. To enhance pre-service teachers' ethical reasoning,
3. To engage pre-service teachers in analyzing real-life teacher leadership cases

The instructional strategies outlined in this article can serve as exemplars for teacher preparation programs aiming to enhance leadership training for pre-service teachers. In line with the assertion by Beyer (1997), as cited by Ewie, C. (2010), that the primary goal of schooling is learning, with learning being a product of thinking, it becomes evident that students' success is intricately linked to their capacity for skillful thinking. While educators have increasingly recognized the importance of fostering critical thinking skills in learners, there needs to be more attention to how teachers should be trained to promote these skills in schools effectively.

This gap is particularly notable in educational planning in African countries, including Ghana, where there has been insufficient consideration of how teacher training institutions can adequately prepare pre-service teachers to enhance students' critical thinking abilities (Acheampong, 2001; Hill, 2000). Improving the quality of students' thinking necessitates skillful teaching, a skill that only emerges through adequate preparation. Consequently, the challenge for pre-service teacher institutions in Ghana is to develop training programs that equip pre-service teachers to cultivate critical thinking skills in their students. It is crucial to integrate activities or strategies into teacher preparation in Ghana that actively foster the thinking skills of student-teachers (Ghana et al./Teacher Education Division/Overseas Development Agency, 1993).

Jaca and Javines (2020) underscored the crucial role of quality pre-service teacher education in ensuring excellence in the Philippines' education system, as mandated by RA 7722, Article 1, Section 1. The imperative is to produce teachers equipped with the necessary knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values for effective teaching, particularly emphasizing proficiency in English, the primary medium of instruction in Secondary schools. The Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 further challenges Teacher Education Institutions to enhance the quality of teacher education programs, aligning with global standards and facilitating positive learning outcomes.

Per CMO No.11 s. 1999, which governs the Student Teaching Program, focuses on preparing globally competitive teachers rooted in Philippine ideals and traditions. During the Student Teaching phase, aspiring teachers gain practical classroom teaching experience under a mentor's guidance. However, a significant challenge observed in student teachers is their communication skills, particularly in English, which are essential for effective classroom instruction. Despite undertaking Communication Arts and Speech classes in their first two years of college, many pre-service teachers need help with their language abilities during classroom discussions. This deficiency in oral communication skills poses a notable gap, as future teachers are expected to communicate fluently in English to deliver lessons seamlessly and engage with students effectively.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The research delves into the competencies essential for career readiness among pre-service teachers, revealing notable variations in mean results across different competencies. Critical thinking and oral/written communication are of particular concern, identified as the least developed among the eight competencies. In light of the challenges brought by the Industrial Revolution 4.0 era, the study emphasizes the urgency of cultivating competent pre-service teachers capable of global competition. Notably, the study highlights the critical importance of teamwork/collaboration and global/intercultural fluency, as evidenced by their highest mean, underscoring their pivotal role in the growth of pre-service teachers and the enhancement of teaching strategies.

Effective collaboration emerges as an imperative for addressing challenges in education, especially the pressing issue of early school leaving. The research underscores the significance of intercultural competence for educators operating within a globally interconnected educational landscape. Furthermore, the study accentuates the pivotal role of professionalism in pre-service teacher education, emphasizing the need to integrate human resources through comprehensive training and program initiatives.

The evolving societal landscape places a premium on new skills, with ICT playing a pivotal role in education. The study asserts that pre-service teachers must be well-prepared for the pedagogical integration of ICT in teaching and learning to meet the demands of this information and knowledge-centric era. External and internal factors influencing prospective teachers' career decisions are thoughtfully explored, emphasizing teachers' multifaceted roles. The research underscores the importance of meticulous selection, practical training, and continuous development to ensure the holistic development of future educators.

The study concludes by stressing the critical need for teachers to comprehend societal changes and possess a comprehensive academic and professional foundation. Additionally, it advocates for teacher leadership, particularly within pre-service teacher training programs, as a catalyst for school improvement. The challenges faced by educational systems in Ghana and the Philippines are outlined, emphasizing the vital role of language proficiency, communication skills, and the imperative to produce globally competitive teachers.

REFERENCE

- Ariff, N., Mansor, M., & Yusof, H. (2017). Preparing pre-service teacher in professionalism practice. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 7(2), 749-756. <http://dx.doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v7-i2/2683>
- Barnatt, J., Andries D'Souza, L., Gleeson, A. M., Mitchell Viesca, K., & Wery, J. (2020). Intercultural competence in pre-service teacher candidates. *International Journal of Educational Reform*, 29(3), 211-235. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1056787919896866>
- Cabezas-González, M., Casillas-Martín, S., & García-Peñalvo, F. J. (2021). The digital competence of pre-service educators: The influence of personal variables. *Sustainability*, 13(4), 2318. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13042318>
- Celik, B. (2017). Career development of teachers: importance and benefits. *International Journal of Social Sciences & Educational Studies*, 4(1), 131-135. <https://doi.org/10.23918/ijsses.v4i1p131>

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Circular Memorandum Order No. 11 Series of 2011. "Revised Policies and Standards for Teacher Education."

- Fikriyati, A., Agustini, R., & Suyatno, S. (2022, January). Pre-service Science Teachers' Critical Thinking Dispositions and Critical Thinking Skills. In Eighth Southeast Asia Design Research (SEA-DR) & the Second Science, Technology, Education, Arts, Culture, and Humanity (STEACH) International Conference (SEADR-STEACH 2021) (pp. 176-181). Atlantis Press. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.211229.028>
- Gentry, R. (2012). Collaboration Skills Pre-Service Teachers Acquire in a Responsive Preparation Program. *Journal of Instructional Pedagogies*, **8**.
- Jaca, C. A. L., & Javines, F. B. (2020). Oral communication needs of pre-service teachers in practice teaching. *Randwick International of Education and Linguistics Science Journal*, **1**(1), 67-73. <https://doi.org/10.47175/rielsj.v1i1.31>
- Jones, S., Lefoe, G., Harvey, M., & Ryland, K. (2012). Distributed leadership: A collaborative framework for academics, executives and professionals in higher education. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, **34**(1), 67-78. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1360080X.2012.642334>
- Owu-Ewie, C. (2010). Developing critical thinking skills of pre-service teachers in Ghana: Teaching methods and classroom ecology. *Academic Leadership: The Online Journal*, **8**(4), 17.
- Republic Act No. 7722. "Higher Education Act of 1994".
- Xu, Y., & Patmor, G. (2012). Fostering Leadership Skills in Pre-Service Teachers. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, **24**(2), 252-256.